

Review

Russell Gilmour, *Just' Natural Trumpet* (Russell Gilmour, 2024.). 268pp. ISBN: 978-1-73-971592-2.

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Russell Gilmour's new treatise explores the evolution of musical performance from the Renaissance until the Age of Enlightenment, when the adoption of Equal Temperament in the tuning of instruments necessitated mechanical devices to give satisfactory intonation on the Trumpet. As early as 1448 the Trumpet Corps of King Christian 1st of Denmark played as an ensemble and by 1607 Claudio Monteverdi was employing 3 trumpeters to open his Opera 'Orpheo'. By the middle of the eighteenth century an astonishing degree of virtuosity was being achieved to be featured in the works of Bach, Handel, Telemann and innumerable others playing upon 'Natural' trumpets which are basically lengths of tubing with a mouthpiece into which to propel vibrating air at one end, and a 'bell' at the other, where the tube expands in order to amplify the resultant sounds.

This book is full of instructional material from the intervening centuries and good, practical advice as to how these materials can be beneficial to students at the present time. A nice touch is that he includes facsimiles of the original manuscripts as well as corresponding examples in clear modern notation. There are also many visual delights in the reproduction of historic paintings and portraits with commentaries and anecdotes from contemporary colleagues, critics, and admirers. Particularly striking for me is the photograph of a sumptuously ornate silver trumpet with solid gold garnishes made in 1581 by Anton Schnitzer of Nuremberg which appears on the opening pages. Also featured is a depiction (tapestry?) of a royal event in 1511 where amongst several trumpeters John Blanke, a black player is seen. He served both king Henry VII and Henry VIII between 1507 and 1512 and must have been valued because at one time his salary was doubled! There is potential for an interesting investigation focusing on John Grano, who first performed Handel's *Water Music* on the Thames in 1717. Whilst interned in the Marshalsea Prison for debt in 1728/9, he discusses in his diary which being visited by 3 black pupils, one of whom—William Douglas, a freed slave from Barbados—was then supplanting him as London's foremost trumpeter. Douglas was evidently strikingly handsome because the 'Ladies of Quality' apparently swooned when he appeared at music festivals, such as Tunbridge Wells.

Another well-known portrait painting, attributed to the artist Michael Dahl, thought to be of another Handelian trumpeter, Valentine Snow, is reproduced; since this book went to press, a sketch has appeared of Purcell's celebrated player John Shore, and this is so strikingly like the individual in this painting that this long-standing attribution may need to be reassessed. In approaching the practicalities of recreating the sound and style of bygone times, a very sensible and mature philosophy is adopted in the opening chapter. The fact of the matter is that, however interesting it is to be 'historically aware', the general public are unlikely to accept untempered intonation any more than the 6 year old Mozart did when his father

blew a (natural) trumpet at him. It was for this reason that in the 1960s, Walter Holy, the trumpet professor in Cologne, developed a venting system with 3 small anti-nodal holes in the tubing to correct the problematic harmonics of the 'natural' scale.

Having been involved in the exciting, somewhat experimental early years of the Early Music movement, working with David Munrow, Christopher Hogwood, Peter Seymour, Peter Holman, and Andrew Parrott, there was a distinct pioneering spirit as we reassessed and rediscovered music of the Baroque era and before – most particularly concerning the speeds and volume of those days, before large symphony orchestras got their hands on it. The theatres and Opera houses of Handel's day were quite large with unreverberant acoustics, but it was with musical spectacles such as the *Music for the Royal Fireworks*, and choruses of hundreds in Westminster Abbey for Messiah in the mid- and late-eighteenth century that the volume notch was turned up. Also around this time, the concept of Equal Temperament was adopted; wherein each semitone of the chromatic scale was equally spaced. J.S. Bach published his 48 Preludes and Fugues as the 'Well Tempered Clavier' between 1722 and 1742, which demonstrated that with this equal spacing of notes you could now play satisfactorily in all major and minor keys. Once out of the bottle, this genie was never replaced in it.

In Purcell's time, concerts usually occurred in a more intimate setting, with the trumpet accompanying a solo singer with just continuo in support, indicating that the instrument was then played with great delicacy. Similarly in Leipzig, Gottfried Reiche, Bach's great trumpeter surely played in a manner that blended with the flutes and oboes rather than overwhelming them. This was the art of 'Clarino'.

In the late-1970s and early-1980s we had to do something that Reiche in Germany and John Shore in England did not have to do: play demanding music over and over again with 100% accuracy for the recording industry. Additionally, our audiences—not to mention the critics—could not contend with what sounded 'out of tune' playing. My great friend and colleague Micheal Laird went to study with Walter Holy, and upon return worked to adapt and improve his system. The arguable drawback with vented trumpets is that they mostly work better with modern mouthpieces, and since all any trumpet does is to amplify the sound (generated by lip vibration) put into it, a player can, and often does, produce the strident frequencies and overtones of a shorter modern trumpet at symphony volume; the deeper, wider mouthpieces of previous times eliminate these high frequencies and are much less strident.

Russell Gilmour looks into every aspect of this lost art in great detail with a multitude of fascinating illustrations. He also confronts pedagogical aspects of his subject starting with the well-known treatises of Caesare Bendinelli and Girolamo Fantini, pointing out the fact that there is a 150 year gap before anything comparable was produced by J.E. Altenburg in 1795. The treatises mostly refer to the articulation of military signals which were a vital ingredient for controlling troop movements on the battlefield, but instruction is also given towards the artistic use of the instrument. During these 150 intervening years there are many references in literature and diaries with cogent observations made by the likes of Samuel Pepys, Johann Matheson, Roger North and James Talbot - all fully quoted in this book.

Fulsome reference is also made to modern pedagogy, in particular the work of Kristian Steenstrup, trumpet professor at Denmark's Royal Academy of Music. Being of the outdated 'just pick it up and blow it' school, I found this interesting but slightly mystifying, as is much of the teaching encountered in my many visits to music universities and faculties in the USA. A more scientific approach to playing exists since I was a student and teacher, but if this helps

young enthusiasts, then so be it.

This excellent book will serve several generations of trumpeters, I hope; it may be for this reason that current practitioners performing on real Natural Trumpets are not mentioned. I never thought I should live to hear the music of Bach and Telemann performed as authentically and accurately as by Jean-Francois Madeuf or Julian Zimmermann. Playing alongside other trumpeters and instrumentalists is vital to prepare for life in the profession. Possibly young players might also find it useful to play along with recordings; it is very important to be able to play not only the solo parts but those of an orchestral section, even the basic trumpet parts in the Symphonies of Mozart and Haydn require skill and musicianship to play well and make very satisfying and excellent training.

I see myself returning to reread this time and time again. Please buy, read, study and cherish this marvellous book.